

A New Model to describe Positive Emotions

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The current paper presents a novel model to describe positive emotions. It bases on a single pleasant emotion (GE) which is perceived bodily by individuals. This pleasant emotion is activated by physical detectors and by eight logical detectors in the case of clearly defined and for the individual potentially favourable circumstances. Those eight logical detectors control survival aspects such as the own goal attainment, the protection of the own resources, the respect for the own personality, own advantages, the stability of the own health, favourable behaviours, and the perception of attractive objects. A similar model has been proposed for negative emotions. The signals of each of those eight logical detectors constitute the basic elements which form the emotions. The model can consistently be explained from an evolutionary perspective. Both emotion models explain various psychological phenomena and improve the understanding, the analysis, and the explanation of emotions substantially.

1. Introduction

The nature of the human emotion system is the subject of various emotion theories [Meyer, 2001; Meyer, 2003; Reisenzein, 2003]. The theories deal with fundamental questions concerning the when, the why, and the how of the activation of emotions. They often focus on historically grown terms of emotions such as fear, anger, disgust, joy, sadness, or the subjective well-being.

Most people agree that emotions appear in two basic qualities: they are either pleasant or unpleasant [Fredrickson, 2008]. Thus positive emotions are distinguished from negative ones. Already Aristotle classified the emotions according to those two dimensions and realized that emotions base on cognition, i.e. on processes of perception and recognition [Aristotle, 350]. Also Spinoza systematically classified the terms of emotions into those two basic classes and defined them appropriately [Spinoza, 1677]. Locke and Leibniz held similar views [Locke, 1690; Leibniz, 1704].

The research focused for a long time on negative emotions. Only in recent times the interest

for the research on positive emotions awoke [Ekman, 2003; Bucher, 2018]. Positive emotions are more difficult to investigate than negative emotions. The reason for this is among other things that positive emotions are less prominent and often have a shorter duration compared to negative emotions. A convincing model which explains their development and their variety in a unique and integrative way is missing so far.

The following thoughts on the description and classification of positive emotions are not based on the ubiquitous terms of emotions. Instead the proposed model is based on the elementary emotion GE, the common denominator of all positive emotions, which can be bodily experienced by the individual. Eight discrete and precisely defined mechanisms, working as logical detectors, activate the elementary emotion GE on a cognitive basis. The signals from those eight logical detectors are the foundation of positive emotions. Together with similar basic elements for negative emotions they enable to describe all emotions and to precisely understand the development and the structure of emotions.

2. The good emotion GE

As described comprehensively [Tscharmi, 2017; Tscharmi, 2019a-c; Tscharmi, 2020] all negative emotions (such as anger, jealousy, homesickness) have a common denominator which can be experienced bodily by the perceiving individual. This common denominator consists of an unpleasant inner uneasiness, the uneasiness emotion UE. It appears typically in a palm-sized area around the navel or a little bit above that. All negative emotions manifest themselves in the form of this UE.

Similarly positive emotions (such as joy, happiness, elation) have a common denominator which can be experienced bodily by the individual. This common denominator consists of a pleasant emotion which is perceived bodily in the head, peripheral below the brain skull. This pleasant emotion is called good emotion, or GE, in the following. All positive emotions manifest themselves by this GE. However, its intensity is much lower than the one of the UE. This makes positive emotions more difficult to observe. In addition, most people feel well already in their normal daily lives [Bless, 1990; Diener, 1996], i.e. they often experience an agreeable actual feeling level (called mood) what decreases the selectivity of an upcoming positive emotion and increases the one of an upcoming negative emotion. And finally, the duration of an evoked GE is typically shorter than the one of an evoked UE.

The GE is a pleasant emotion. Its pleasant and agreeable character rewards the individual for a certain occurrence (for example for a goal attainment, for a respect for the own personality by a different individual, for the perception of an attractive object). At the same time it motivates the individual to achieve a comparable situation in the future in order to experience the pleasant GE again. This can be seen very well in the human addiction behaviour: addicted persons take again and again the addictive drug or show an addiction behaviour which is characterized by repetition in order to experience the resulting GE again – even if those persons neglect or damage other areas of their lives. The enormous power of this GE can be seen in experiments. The Americans Olds and Milner provided rats with a button by which they could generate good feelings in their brains. The rats began to press this button non-stop. They neglected all other activities, even the ingestion of food, and not even painful electric shocks stopped them from pressing the button. They pressed the button until they collapsed

because of exhaustion [Olds, 1956; Eibl-Eibesfeldt, 1967].

Like the UE the GE is a universal feeling, i.e. it can be activated by completely different occurrences (or triggers). These triggers can be divided into two groups. Simple GE triggers activate the GE according to a certain body state (e.g. because of the ingestion of food, bowel movement, or orgasm). They directly base on signals from physical receptors which are specialized to measure those body states. Cognitive GE triggers activate the GE by means of logical detection. They signal a higher processed occurrence (e.g. the perception of a protection for a significant own resource). Cognitive GE triggers base on indirectly derived information (e.g. visual, acoustic, stored information) from already otherwise existing signals. Regardless how different the GE triggers (or detectors) are, they always activate one and the same, equally felt good emotion GE.

The GE and the UE constitute the basic elements of all emotions. Therefore they are called elementary emotions in the following. They make it easy to distinguish emotions from other feelings (such as a pinch, a feeling of warmth, or a headache) [Tscharmi, 2020].

The GE fundamentally differs from the so-called mood. The mood denotes the actual, often longer lasting (i.e. hours, days) subjectively experienced feeling level which an individual experiences. The mood always exists, also if there are no currently active simple or cognitive impulses (or emotions, respectively). As already mentioned most people usually feel well, i.e. they experience usually a good mood [Bless, 1990; Diener, 1996]. Upcoming UE impulses can lower this basic feeling level, upcoming GE impulses can raise the mood. Also other external or internal factors influence the mood. For example, the mood of many individuals is better on sunny than on rainy days [Schwarz, 1987a]. Similarly the “accidental” finding of a dime on a copy machine enhances the mood of many people. The mood improves also if the favourite soccer team wins an important game [Schwarz, 1987b]. Pain or ongoing unpleasant sensations (e.g. during the PMS, during hunger) lower the mood. The mood is active in the background of the consciousness whereas the simple and cognitive impulses (or the emotions, respectively) push themselves to the forefront [Fredrickson, 2008]. Since the mood does not necessarily activate an elementary emotion it does not count to the emotions but to the feelings (of the FSW class, see below).

3. Feelings, emotions, and thoughts

Various information appear in the consciousness of an individual. This information can be grouped into three categories: sensory impressions from specialized sensors of the body, feelings, and thoughts (for an extensive description see [Tscharmi, 2020]).

The first category comprises the sensory impressions. Sensory impressions shall include all information which come from specialized physical sensors or receptors of the body. Examples for sensory impressions include the vision, the hearing, or the sense of smell.

The second category includes all feelings. The category of the feelings and the category of the sensory impressions have a common intersection. As their name indicates feelings describe bodily perceptible information. It is part of their nature that acute feelings are bound to specific locations of the body. The category of the feelings splits into the classes of the feeling-based sensory impressions without elementary emotions (FSW), the emotions, and the seeming symptoms.

The class of the feeling-based sensory impressions without elementary emotions (FSW) comprises all sensory impressions which come from physical receptors of the body, which can be felt, but which do not necessarily include an elementary emotion. The FSW include almost all of the various body sensations, such as the pain, the (gentle) touch, the pinch, the burn, the feeling of cold, the feeling of warmth, the thirst, or the pressure sense.

All feelings which necessarily activate an elementary emotion (the UE or the GE) are denoted by the term “emotion” in the following and are part of the class of the emotions. Thus emotions are a subset of the feelings and have in addition a common intersection with the sensory impressions (which includes for example the hunger, the urgent need to empty the bowels, and the bowel movement).

The seeming symptoms denote upcoming feelings without a physical or a logical (i.e. based on logical detection) cause (e.g. the phantom pain).

The third category of information which appears in the consciousness consists of the thoughts. Thoughts denote all information appearing in the consciousness of an individual which are neither a sensory impression nor a feeling. Thoughts appear in humans in visual or in linguistic form. The category of thoughts splits into the class of automatic thoughts and the class of voluntary thoughts. Many thoughts appear automatically, i.e. without any active effort, in the consciousness of the perceiving individual (the so-called automatic thoughts) [Beck, 1976]. Already Leibniz described such unwilling and uncalled thoughts and denoted them as “flying thoughts”, which are not within our power [Leibniz, 1704]. Such automatic thoughts can prevent the individual from falling asleep or spoil a longer waiting time for him or her. On the other hand, if a person formulates a certain content consciously and deliberately (for example the sentence “Now I am thinking deliberately.”) only in his or her mind without saying it, then a voluntary thought is created.

4. The GE impulses

4.1 Simple GE impulses

Simple GE triggers (or detectors) activate the elementary emotion GE directly by signals which are delivered by *physical* receptors (or sensors, respectively) which are specialized in the surveillance of the corresponding state of the body. Simple GE impulses include the ingestion of food, the bowel movement, the micturition, the sexual activity, and the orgasm. All those body states activate the pleasant elementary emotion GE automatically. This activation happens by signals from specialized receptors which monitor the corresponding body states. For example, the GE which is activated in humans by the bowel movement is based on signals of receptors in the area of the anus which register the passage of the stool (a fact that Japanese toilet manufactures know since a long time). Thus, the release of the pleasant GE by simple GE triggers bases on clearly defined and measurable quantities. Some of the simple GE impulses appear together with other feelings (of the FSW class). Note however, that an individual perceives those signals only if it is not distracted by other things (for example by thoughts).

The activated pleasant GE rewards the individual for a certain behaviour or for a certain occurrence, for example in case of hunger for the ingestion of food. At the same time this

reward is an incentive for the individual to behave in a similar way in the future in order to experience the pleasant GE again.

4.2 Cognitive GE impulses

In contrary to simple GE triggers the activation of the pleasant GE by cognitive GE triggers bases not on specialized physical receptors but on *logical* detectors which are based on a pure information processing of already otherwise existing information (e.g. visible, audible, stored information). A cognition occurs, for example in the form of a pattern recognition [Stein, 1990]. Thus, the cognitive activation of the GE is based on an indirect determination of the desired parameters. The activated GE then signals to the individual the result of this information processing (e.g. the perception of a furtherance of an own important striving, the perception of a respect for the own personality by a different individual, the perception of an own advantage).

The activation of a cognitive GE impulse follows clearly defined rules and is based on the perception of a specific fact or a specific occurrence (e.g. a goal attainment). Therefore the signals of the GE detectors often manifest like an impulse, i.e. they appear suddenly and causally. Dependent on the specific situation, the activated GE then lasts for a longer or shorter period of time.

Eight different cognitive GE triggers (or GE detectors) can be distinguished. They generate eight different cognitive GE impulses: ITWOUT, NOTINA, RESPECT, HAVAD, DOWEL, UDIR, IDIR, and LIKIT. They are described in detail in the following. The situation resembles the one in the UE area where also eight cognitive UE impulses appear (ITNOUT, SOTINA, NESPECT, HASAD, NOWEL, UDINOR, IDINOR, and DISLIKIT¹).

Occasionally cognitive GE impulses are accompanied by other feelings (e.g. of the FSW class).

But first some remarks to the nomenclature. All GE triggers activate one and the same GE. Dependent on the specific situation, this GE can appear stronger, weaker, longer, or shorter but it always appears in the same, bodily experienced, pleasant form. In order to be able to distinguish the different signals from the different cognitive GE detectors, the former are given different names which refer to the activated GE detector (or to the reason of the activation, respectively). For example, ITWOUT denotes the GE which is activated by the ITWOUT detector. Analogously, NOTINA denotes the GE which is activated by the NOTINA detector. The ITWOUT detector detects ITWOUT situations (i.e. situations in which a furtherance of an own important striving appears); the NOTINA detector detects NOTINA situations (i.e. situations in which a protection for an own significant resource is perceived).

After those remarks it will be described in the following in detail when precisely a (cognitive) activation of the pleasant GE takes place in an individual. Such a GE is generated in eight different situations, namely at

– a furtherance of an own striving (ITWOUT),

¹ The eight abbreviations denote [Tscharmi, 2020]: ITNOUT: “It does not work out (like I want it to)”, SOTINA: “Somebody takes something away from me”, NESPECT: “I am not respected”, HASAD: “He/she/it has an advantage”, NOWEL: “I do not feel well”, UDINOR: “You did something not right”, IDINOR: “I did something not right”, DISLIKIT: “I dislike it/this”.

- a protection of an own resource (NOTINA),
- a respect for the own personality (RESPECT),
- a perception of an own advantage (HAVAD),
- a perception of a stability of the own physical integrity (DOWEL),
- a favourable behaviour of a different power (UDIR),
- a favourable own behaviour (IDIR), and
- a perception of an attractive object (LIKIT).

4.2.1 Furtherance of an own striving: ITWOUT

Definition: *ITWOUT* [itwaʊt] (abbreviation of “*It* *does* *work* *out* (like I want it to)”) denotes the GE which develops automatically from the perception of a furtherance of an own important striving.

The ITWOUT detector reacts on a real or probable furtherance of an own important striving. If the detector recognizes such a furtherance then a signal in the form of the pleasant GE is released in the perceiving individual.

In the focus of this cognitive GE impulse is the furtherance of an own striving. The activation of ITWOUT requires that the perceiving individual strives for an explicit or implicit goal. This goal can be of short-term or of long-term nature. Striving means that the individual itself would like to achieve this goal [Hoppe, 1931; Oishi, 1999] – be it through one’s own or through somebody else’s activity (i.e. through a particular action or omission). Thus striving bases on an underlying own goal of the individual. Examples for such a striving are to reach a different place, to get or ingest food, to realize an activity, to communicate with a different individual, to get a certain information or object, to bring a different individual or an object to a desired behaviour, or to build or to destroy something. Moreover, at the current moment the individual considers it as important to reach its goal. The prerequisite for the activation of ITWOUT is thus an own striving which is important to individual (at the current moment). During its striving the individual then perceives a furtherance by an internal or external (i.e. different from the own body) power. This power has a material or an immaterial consistence and is part of the living world (of the same species or of a different species) or of the inanimate world. A power of the living world can be a single individual or a group of individuals (including an organisation). Examples for such a power include a different individual (e.g. the parents, the partner, colleagues, employees, animals, plants), the perceiving individual itself, an inanimate object (e.g. a device), natural forces (e.g. beautiful weather, the right breeze for sailing, gravity), chance (e.g. coincidence), or an intellectual object (e.g. a riddle). Many human cultures assign imaginary personifications and names to powers of the inanimate world or the living world (such as goddess of fertility, god of weather, god of war, goddess of hunting, goddess of love, goddess of chance). Furtherance means that things develop as desired or better than expected. A furtherance develops because of a favourable behaviour or a favourable property of the underlying power. The furtherance (potentially) fosters the goal attainment. Examples of such a furtherance include a favourable property or behaviour of an inanimate object (e.g. an unusual longevity of a product, an ease of use of a device), a favourable property or behaviour of other individuals (e.g. an efficiently working employee, the successful offspring, the glorious

favourite soccer team), a favourable own property or behaviour (e.g. the independent cycling for the first time, a flow at work, an own sporting success, a good own look), a favourable property or behaviour of natural forces (e.g. beautiful weather, following wind during cycling, journey down on a bicycle), a favourable effect by chance or coincidence (e.g. a bus which arrives just in the right moment, low traffic on the highway), or a favourable property of an intellectual object (e.g. a soluble riddle).

For example ITWOUT can appear during solving a Sudoku riddle. The latter requires to complete a two-dimensional quadratic matrix consisting of numbers in such a way that each number appears precisely once in each row and once in each column. Such a matrix is called a Latin square. Latin squares were first described in detail by the probably world's best mathematician Leonhard Euler [Euler, 1782]. Today their influence extends as far as into the area of all-optical networks [Gipser, 1996a; Gipser 1996b]. The successful solution of a riddle such as Sudoku tends to motivate an individual to engage again in such a task in the future whereas a failure fosters a dislike of such challenges [Hoppe, 1931].

Like this is the case at cognitive UE impulses it is also for the cognitive GE impulses crucial that an individual actually perceives (or recognizes) the corresponding situation (here: a real or potential furtherance). Only under this condition a cognitive GE impulse can be generated. If an individual does not perceive an occurring furtherance, for example because it is distracted by other events or by thoughts, then no ITWOUT impulse appears.

ITWOUT is a pleasant emotion. The perception of a furtherance of an own important striving generates a pleasant emotion [Srull, 1986; Fredrickson, 2008; Hill, 2008]. The intensity of this GE typically ranges from small to intermediate, sometimes it reaches high values. The activated GE can appear in different expressions. Expressions denote different terms for the GE in different situations. Sometimes expressions go along with changes in physiology, body language, accompanying (secondary) feelings (for example of the FSW class), or behaviour. Typical expressions of ITWOUT are joy, happiness, thankfulness, contentment, confidence, a feeling of success, enthusiasm, a feeling of triumph, or elation.

Beside the GE automatic thoughts (i.e. automatically generated thoughts) appear in an ITWOUT situation (i.e. a situation in which ITWOUT dominates). These automatic thoughts focus on the cause of the GE generation, i.e. on the furtherance of an own important striving which has been perceived. Their contents are often of descriptive nature (“Ah, here comes the desired underground.”) or of commenting character (“Super!”; “Everything works out like planned.”).

In and after an ITWOUT situation individuals show different types of behaviour. Those include to smile, to laugh, to cheer (for example by raising the arms [Eibl-Eibesfeldt, 1967] or the clenched fists, by raising one fist, by splaying the index finger and the middle finger to the V-sign [Morris, 1994]), to continue the current own striving [Hoppe, 1931], to approach the reason of the furtherance in a friendly (verbally, non-verbally, physically) or unfriendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically (including elimination, e.g. to hunt and kill the spotted animal)), to (correctly) attribute a self-achieved success to an own behaviour, to (wrongly) attribute a success generated by external circumstances to an own behaviour, to communicate with other individuals about the furtherance or the success, to celebrate the success, to stop the current own striving [Hoppe, 1931], or to omit any special activities. Often the individual strives to repeat the success (and thus the activation of the pleasant ITWOUT).

If the pursuance of an activity leads to a sequence of furtherances, which continuously bring the individual closer to its goal, then the arising and lasting pleasant experience is called a *flow* [Csikszentmihalyi, 1990]. Then the pursued activity is a pleasant flow of successive

single steps which activate each ITWOUT- (and IDIR-) impulses, induce a positive mood and gradually lead to the desired result. The own doing, the requirements, and the external circumstances ideally fit together.

The mechanism which leads to the activation of ITWOUT in the individual corresponds to a furtherance detector. This detector knows the explicit and implicit goals of the individual and rewards the latter for a discovered furtherance with a GE impulse. This reward shall motivate the individual to repeat own behaviours which possibly lead to the furtherance. The functional equivalent of the ITWOUT impulse consists in the cognitive UE impulse ITNOUT in the UE area. The mechanism which activates ITNOUT corresponds to a hindrance detector since it discovers hindrances of a current striving of the individual. Both mechanisms (which activate the contrasting pair ITNOUT–ITWOUT) control the goal attainment of the individual. This function corresponds to a goal attainment detector. The latter automatically checks perceived occurrences concerning their influence on the goals or the plans of the individual.

4.2.2 Protection of an own resource: NOTINA

Definition: *NOTINA* [nəʊtana] (abbreviation of “*Nobody takes something away from me*”) denotes the GE which develops automatically from the perception of a protection for an own significant resource.

The availability of (sufficient) own resources is crucial for the survival of the genes of an individual. Therefore the protection of own significant resources is of fundamental importance. The NOTINA detector registers the protection of own significant resources. If such a real or putative protection is perceived then a signal in the form of the pleasant GE (NOTINA) is activated.

The centre of this cognitive GE impulse is the protection of own resources. Already Maslow named the perception of protection and security as a basic need of an individual and assigned it a prominent place in its hierarchy of needs [Maslow, 1954]. Analogously Scott regards the shelter- and comfort-seeking behaviour as a fundamental kind of behaviour of individuals. The latter can be observed from the vertebrates to the protozoa [Scott, 1969].

The prerequisite for the generation of NOTINA in an individual is the existence of an own significant resource. A resource of an individual includes anything what is able to generate a positive (i.e. a pleasant) feeling in the perceiving individual. Such a resource has a material or an immaterial consistence and is part of the living world (of the same species or of a different species) or of the inanimate world. The resource can also be owned by a different individual, nevertheless the former is able to generate positive (i.e. pleasant) feelings in the perceiving individual. The resource has to be significant for the individual, i.e. the resource has to have a positive meaning for the perceiving individual. Examples for the resources of a human include a beloved partner, beloved children, pets, food, possession, property (e.g. a territory, a real estate, an intellectual property), fortune, own abilities, power, the own health, hobbies, preferences, persons of public life that he or she likes, or splendid public buildings. The resources of children include the parents, the doll, or soft toys (for example the teddy bear).

This resource stays with the individual, i.e. the perceiving individual is certain that no other power takes the resource away from him or her. The individual believes the resource safe. The internal or external (i.e. different from the own body) power which could take away the resource has a material or an immaterial consistence and is part of the living world (of same

species or of a different species) or of the inanimate world. A power of the living world can be a single individual or a group of individuals (including an organization). Examples for such a power are volcanic eruptions, flashes of lightning, fires, conflagrations, deep or raging waters, tsunamis, drought, strong winds, severe cold or heat, dangerous submarine cliffs or shoals, earthquakes, avalanches, moving detritus, very confined caves, harmful substances, dangerous radiation, gravity, thieves, defrauders, murderers, criminal organizations, war, vehicles of all kind (on a collision course) including aircraft, water-craft and spacecraft, a high voltage, predators, poisonous plants or animals, pests, huge swarms of locusts, dangerous viruses, bacteria or fungi, severe diseases, senescence, and evil spirits.

But the individual thinks its resource safe. The resource is protected. The stock of the individual remains unchanged. The reason that an individual believes its resources safe relies on the fact that there is currently no hostile power (e.g. predators, thieves, thunderstorms) in his or her environment, that the individual does not know the hostile power, that the latter has no access on the resources of the individual, or that a stronger protecting power can cover the hostile power. Such a protecting power has a material or an immaterial consistence and is part of the living world (of the same species or of a different species) or of the inanimate world. A power of the living world can be a single individual or a group of individuals (including an organization). Examples for such a protecting power include for small children the mother, a safe accommodation or shelter, a safe place, lightning conductors, dams, warming clothes, heating, avalanche barriers, protective clothing, sunglasses, suntan lotion, crash-barriers and railings, the fire brigade, rescue services, the police, bodyguards, protecting dogs, the peace movement and relief organizations, safety regulations of all kind, safety glass and belts, fuses, back-up copies, the knowledge about harmful plants or animals, hygiene, vaccination, and protecting spirits. Many human cultures assign tutelary gods to dangerous phenomena of the inanimate world and the living world (e.g. a goddess of volcano, a god of thunder, a god of earth quakes, a god of flooding, a goddess of the cooking fire, a god of fire, a god of seafaring, a goddess of peace). Children often treat their soft toys like living creatures and assign protective qualities to them what provides the children a pleasant NOTINA. The classic example from the realm of NOTINA is the mother who holds her child on her lap. The individual has to perceive the fact of a real or probable protection of an own significant resource in order to enable an activation of NOTINA. If this perception is missing then no NOTINA impulse is generated. The probability of such a perception increases when the availability of such a protection is no naturalness.

The NOTINA called GE is per se pleasant. This GE, which is generated by the perception of a protection for an own significant resource, appears often with a small to intermediate intensity in the individual. Typical expressions (or overall emotional manifestations) of the GE are an inner calmness, security, a feeling of safety, happiness, thankfulness, relief, relaxation, and sometimes also carelessness.

In a NOTINA situation (i.e. a situation in which NOTINA dominates) automatic thoughts (in the form of pictures or language) are frequently generated. Such automatic thoughts centre on the cause of the generation of the GE, i.e. on the protection of an own significant resource. They are of descriptive nature (“Here I am safe.”) or of commenting nature (“Wonderful!”). In and after a NOTINA situation individuals show different types of behaviour. The latter typically include to smile, to approach the protection in a friendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically), to communicate with other individuals about the protection or the own resource, to openly show the own resource (without protecting it particularly), or to omit any special activities. Also in order to experience NOTINA again in the future individuals often

strive to repeat such a protection or to enhance the latter.

An obvious consequence of the cognitive GE impulse NOTINA can be seen in lullabies. Lullabies often have harmonious melodies which babies prefer to dissonant tunes [Zentner, 1996]. The contents of lullabies worldwide frequently are about protection and safety [Spitzer, 2002] and are variations in the form of: “Fall asleep. The mother is here. You are safe. Everything is all right.” Furthermore it is sung the praises of how peaceful the environment of the baby is right now: the father tends the sheep, the kitten climbs a large tree, the bees are humming, and the stars are sparkling in the sky. As guarantors for the safety angels, saints, or tutelary gods keep watch over the cradle. Lullabies were already present in the ancient Rome and at the ancient Greeks [Brakeley, 1950].

Other consequences of NOTINA can be seen when visiting a restaurant. In the restaurant people first take the tables on the corner and the ones along the wall – they convey a plus of safety because then nobody can stay in the back of the individual – and in the end the free-standing tables. Children feel well in niches and like to build such a cover [Eibl-Eibesfeldt, 1967].

The mechanism which generates NOTINA in the individual works like a protection detector. The mechanism recognizes that a certain resource is safe and activates the pleasant GE. The latter rewards the individual for the actually perceived protection. Analogously its corresponding mechanism in the UE area, which activates SOTINA, works like a taking away detector. The latter warns the individual with an unpleasant UE impulse if or before it loses a significant resource. Together both mechanisms (which release the contrasting pair SOTINA–NOTINA) work like a safety detector which continuously controls the safety of the resources of the perceiving individual.

4.2.3 Respect for the own personality: RESPECT

Definition: *RESPECT* [rɪspekt] (abbreviation of “I am respected”) denotes the GE which develops automatically from the perception of a respect for the own personality.

The recognition of well-disposed and respectful other individuals is of fundamental importance for the shaping of the social and sexual relationships of an individual. A specialized GE detector, the RESPECT detector, therefore reacts to signs of a respect for the own personality. If it detects such a real or supposed respect then it generates a signal in the form of the pleasant GE (RESPECT) in the perceiving individual.

Thus the cognitive GE impulse RESPECT refers to the very own part of any individual: the own personality. The personality of an individual includes all characteristics which make it out as a living being. The structure of the personality can be divided into four components: into the physical structure (e.g. the look, the age, the constitution, the health), the intellectual structure (e.g. the knowledge, the intelligence, the mental processes), the own values (e.g. the wishes, the will, the values of the individual value system, its opinions, its expectations), and the behaviour (e.g. the doing, the disposition, the temperament, the achievements, the acquisitions).

The own personality is then treated respectfully by an external (i.e. different from the own body) power. This power is virtually always a part of the living world, i.e. the respect comes from one or several individuals of the same species or of a different species. These individuals are often directly associated with the life of the perceiving individual. Examples for such a

power include the parents, teachers, friends, colleagues, partners, significant others, children, superiors, the own dog, flatterers, charmers, and seducers.

The respect takes place in a verbal, non-verbal, or physical form. Humans react highly sensitive to such signals. Some of those signals are dependent on culture, others are understandable independent of the culture or of the species (e.g. to caress an individual). There is a multitude of forms of respect which has to be learned by a (young) individual. Verbal forms of respect include to be greeted, to be said goodbye, to be addressed with one's name or title, to be praised, to be admired, and to get an excuse. Also in the non-verbal area there is a large number of gestures of respect. The probably best-known gesture is the kiss. Its most intimate form is the kiss onto the lips (or the French kiss). The friendly kiss onto or beside the cheek serves as a sign of greeting or of saying goodbye. Among lovers the kiss onto the neck is widespread. In the western world an indicated kiss on the back of the hand is a respectful greeting of ladies. Another worldwide gesture of respect is to bend the upper part of the body towards the interlocutor what signals attention. A worldwide gesture of greeting (with exception of the USA) is the respectful bowing of the upper part of the body. Another gesture of greeting in western countries is to shortly lift the hat or to shortly tip one's brim of the hat. A worldwide gesture is to shake hands in order to greet somebody or to say goodbye, although this gesture exists not until the beginning of the nineteenth century – before that were bow, curtsy, and waving typical forms of greeting. However, one should keep in mind that in most Islamic countries it is not allowed that a man touches a woman with whom he is not closely related to. If in those countries a male visitor politely tries to shake hands with a woman then this behaviour is considered as a rude impertinence. A widely known gesture is to raise one's hand in greeting [Eibl-Eibesfeldt, 1967]. Also to wave the hand to say goodbye or as an excuse are worldwide known gestures. Special gestures which are dependent on culture include to press both hands toward the own heart (this symbolizes great respect in Taiwan), to smooth with the fingers over the own chin (what means respect in Saudi Arabia), or in the mutual touch of the noses (which is a friendly form of greeting for example among the Maoris in New Zealand) [Morris, 1994]. Often the smile is used as a friendly non-verbal signal, for example in order to greet somebody.

Four different kinds of respect can be distinguished. This first kind of respect is the (direct or indirect, verbal, non-verbal, or physical) *support* of the individual (for example to his opinion or his doing). Examples for such a support include to receive encouragement, agreement, compliments, presents, financial support, promotions; furthermore the consideration of the wishes and requests of the perceiving individual, the keeping of secrets and confidentialities, the honesty towards the perceiving individual, and the defence of the individual against third parties. A second form of respect is the pure *taking notice* of an individual (by greeting, by saying goodbye, by showing respect). The third kind of respect is a *true interest* in the individual (e.g. by an interested listening, by fans in their pop star idol). And the fourth kind of respect is a *desired interest* (for example in the form of a returned love, in the form of tender loving care).

An activation of NESPECT requires finally that the individual actually perceives the real or likely respect for him or her. If this is not the case then no RESPECT impulse is generated. The RESPECT called GE is per se pleasant. This GE, which is activated by the perception of a respect for the own personality, can appear with a high intensity, i.e. in a very pleasant way. Typical expressions (or overall emotional manifestations) of this GE include joy, happiness, thankfulness, or elevation.

Beside the GE automatic thoughts often appear in a RESPECT situation (i.e. in a situation in

which RESPECT prevails). Their contents refer to the cause of the activation of the GE, i.e. the respect for the own personality which has been perceived. They are typically of descriptive nature (“He has the same view.”) or of commenting nature (“Fine. That’s nice.”). In and after a RESPECT situation individuals have different behavioural options. Typical options include to smile, to laugh, to approach the other power in a friendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically), to communicate with other individuals about the perceived respect, to express one’s thanks for the respect, or to omit any corresponding activities. Often the individual tries to get similar signs of respect again in the future by behaving appropriately. Also a mirroring of the behaviour of a different individual (or an unconscious behavioural mimicry, respectively) can activate RESPECT in the other individual. Mirroring means that some behaviours of the other individual are directly imitated. Mirroring often happens unconsciously (for example between girlfriends). It signals attention, agreement, and respect to the other individual. A study showed that subjects who were mimicked by their interlocutor liked this confederate more than those who were not and got the impression that the interaction was more harmonious [Lakin, 2003]. Behavioural mimicry can also be observed in the animal kingdom, for example in the courtship display of birds.

An interesting interhuman consequence of the cognitive GE impulse RESPECT consists in the *Pygmalion effect*. Pygmalion was an inspired sculptor of the Greek antiquity. After the creation of perfect statues of the Greek gods the bachelor decided one day to create a statue of a perfect virgin. Hardly had he accomplished the work of art which was of incomparable beauty, he fell in undying love with his work. But his perfect beloved could not reply his love since she was made of cold stone. This aroused the pity of the Greek gods, they breathed life into the statue such that it became a human being of flesh and blood, descended from her pedestal, and lived happily together with Pygmalion until the end of their days. Thus, the idea of Pygmalion became a reality. This concept is also the base of the Pygmalion effect. If for example a superior or a teacher has a positive opinion about an employee or a student then he or she will convey his or her opinion directly or indirectly to this individual. This respect activates RESPECT in the individual and motivates it to fulfil the positive opinion of the superior or the teacher also in the future. The individual works more, learns more intensively, and improves therefore his or her performance – what in turn confirms the view of the superior or the teacher: his or her idea became a reality. A positive view towards employees or students thus improves their performance on average. Of course also the contrary works out: a negative attitude towards an individual generates NESPECT in this individual, has a demoralizing effect, and tends to decrease his or her performance.

The cognitive GE impulse RESPECT has also a strong effect on the choice of *friends*. People tend to choose friends who are similar to them. In the childhood this similarity mainly concentrates on common activities (especially on common playing). Later in life similar interests and similar character traits gain in importance. An important component in a friendship consists in the impression that one matters to the friend [Demir, 2011]. However, how long a friendship lasts depends significantly on how many mutual RESPECT impulses are generated and how many NESPECT impulses are prevented.

The mechanism which generates RESPECT in the individual works like a respect detector. In a similar way the mechanism which generates NESPECT in the UE area can be seen as a disrespect detector. Together both social detectors (which activate the contrasting pair NESPECT–RESPECT) work like a friendliness detector which constantly checks and assesses the friendliness of other individuals towards the perceiving individual.

4.2.4 Perception of an own advantage: HAVAD

Definition: *HAVAD* [hævæd] (abbreviation of “*I have an advantage*”) denotes the GE which develops automatically from the perception of an own advantage regarding a resource which is claimed by the perceiving individual.

The perception of an advantage regarding its own resources compared to those of a different individual is potentially advantageous for the survival of the genes of the perceiving individual. Thus the HAVAD detector reacts to own advantages of resources which are claimed by the individual. If it detects a corresponding real or probable own advantage it activates a signal in the form of the pleasant GE (HAVAD).

Like in the case of NOTINA the cognitive impulse HAVAD bases on an own resource. This resource has a material or an immaterial consistence and is part of the living world (of the same species or of a different species) or of the inanimate world. Examples for such a resource are food, a toy, possessions of all kind (like a watch, a car, a painting), attributes (e.g. beautiful hair, a slim figure, intelligence), money, success, an accommodation (e.g. an apartment, a house), a mate, status symbols, power, attention of other individuals, publicity, happiness, or youthfulness.

The perceiving individual likes to own this resource. This claim of ownership is of critical importance for the activation of HAVAD. Without such a claim of ownership there is no activation of HAVAD in the perceiving individual.

The perceiving individual automatically compares its own situation with the one of a different power. The comparability of these two situations is virtually irrelevant. That means that the HAVAD detector automatically compares also situations with each other which are very different.

The own resource is compared to the one of a different power. This power is almost always a different individual which is almost always of the same species (rarely it consists of a group of individuals). Examples for such a power are siblings, classmates, fellow students, colleagues, superiors, friends, neighbours, persons in public life, and sometimes even the own children.

The comparison now reveals an advantage for the perceiving individual (this comparison is therefore also called a downward comparison). Four different kinds of advantages can be distinguished. In case of an *absolute advantage* only the perceiving individual (but not the other power) possesses the resource. In case of a *quantitative advantage* the perceiving individual possesses an advantageous (often larger) number of units concerning the resource (for example a higher salary, a larger property, a younger woman, a wealthier man). In case of a *qualitative advantage* the individual perceives a better composition of the own resource (e.g. a faster car, a more beautiful dress, spontaneously a better own state of health in the waiting room of a doctor's practice). In case of a *relative advantage* finally, the other power possesses a quantitatively and qualitatively better resource, but nevertheless the perceiving individual recognizes an own advantage, for example because the other power has a total claim of ownership and would like to own also the resource of the perceiving individual (like a real estate owner who would like to own also the real estate of the perceiving individual). Generally for all cognitive impulses (and thus also for the cognitive GE impulse HAVAD) applies the trivial rule that an individual has to perceive a real or probable own advantage (compared to a different individual) before HAVAD can be generated. Without such a perception no activation of HAVAD takes place.

The HAVAD called GE is per se pleasant. This GE, which is generated by the perception of

an own advantage regarding a resource which is claimed by the perceiving individual, has typically a small to intermediate intensity. Typical expressions (or overall emotional manifestations) range from happiness, contentment, thankfulness, self-affirmation, and pride of possession to a feeling of superiority, arrogance, superciliousness, and an ecstasy of power. In a HAVAD situation (i.e. a situation in which HAVAD dominates) automatic thoughts often come up. They focus on the cause of the generated GE, i.e. the perceived own advantage. The content of those automatic thoughts is of descriptive nature (“I have the highest salary in my department.”), of commenting nature (“That’s great.”), of the own advantage justifying nature (“My advantage is well deserved.”), or of inflated character (“I am the best.”).

In and after a HAVAD situation individuals often show typical behaviours. Those include to smile, to laugh, to cheer, to approach the own advantage or the other power in a friendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically; e.g. to console the loser, self-adulation), to approach the other power or the other resource in an unfriendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically; e.g. to attack the loser, to steal the resource), to obtain an even bigger advantage for oneself (also in the form of an acquisitive greed), to communicate with other individuals about the own advantage, to put the own advantage on show (also to boast about it), or to omit any special activities. In order to experience even more HAVAD impulses in the future an individual can decide to extend its claim of possession to further or other resources.

A study revealed that the winners of an Olympic bronze medal are often happier about their ranking than the winners of the silver medal [Medvec, 1995]. The winner of an Olympic bronze medal knows that he or she almost had won no medal at all and almost only had achieved the fourth rank. The comparison of the own situation with the one of the person who finished fourth leads to the pleasant HAVAD in the perceiving individual.

A well-known consequence of HAVAD is that people often assess their own abilities or properties as above-average. Be it the own abilities in driving, the own performance in the job, or the own interhuman capabilities: on average humans assess their own possibilities as being above-average. But if one applies the classic Gaussian normal distribution to the distribution of a certain trait in the population then it proves to be impossible that most people can be better than all others. The reason for this biased positive self-assessment is based on the pleasant action of HAVAD: it feels much better to see oneself as being above-average than to look at average or even below average own abilities.

A further ubiquitous consequence of HAVAD can be seen in the acquisition or display of prestigious or luxurious objects. Such objects remember the individual to their own advantages compared to other individuals and foster the activation of HAVAD and thus of pleasant emotions. They emphasize the impression of the own exclusiveness. Luxury brands serve precisely this market segment.

HAVAD implicitly fosters the accumulation of own resources. However, because resources are often scarce (not everyone can be a millionaire) such efforts inevitably often take place at the expense of other individuals. Thus the winner in the striving for scarce resources fosters its advantages at the expense of the loser [Eibl-Eibesfeldt, 1967]. The striving to accumulate own resources or to feather one’s nest at the expense of other people can be seen in diverse areas, for example in exaggerated salaries of members of the board, in the sale of low-quality or harmful products, in cheatings, in greed, or in waging war.

Furthermore, the pleasant emotion HAVAD can encourage a striving for power and the perception of an own high-handedness. Rulers in the past saw themselves often as godlike beings and classified themselves higher than every other being in this world. King Ludwig XIV. named himself in the 17th and 18th century as the Sun King and hold the view: “L’état

c'est moi.” (“The state that's me.”) His wars of conquest initiated the economic decline of France. According to Nietzsche striving for power aims mainly at the “sight of the conquered”. Lersch writes that a striving for power is not carried out in order to realize factual goals but “merely with the idea of having the perception of power and right of disposal” [Lersch, 1938].

Stereotypes towards other individuals or groups of individuals also activate HAVAD since they always refer to other individuals and since the debasement of others implies an own advantage. Nationalism and racism base therefore on HAVAD. Nationalistic and racist views tend to devalue other nations or races. This gets the individual to believe without reason that he or she is superior and generates the pleasant HAVAD. In consequence less human rights are conceded to other people than to the members of the own nation or race.

The mechanism which activates HAVAD corresponds to a detector for own advantages. Analogously the generation of HASAD in the UE area corresponds to a detector for advantages of a different individual. Together both mechanisms (which activate the contrasting pair HASAD–HAVAD) work like an advantage detector which permanently checks the resources of other individuals in the environment of the perceiving individual and discovers advantages of others or own advantages.

Interestingly, the rules for the activation of HAVAD and HASAD reveal that there exists (from an emotional point of view) no innate sense of justice which would always plead for an objectively fair distribution of resources. Of course the advantages of other individuals can activate the unpleasant HASAD and protest in the perceiving individual. However, own advantages always lead via the generation of HAVAD to pleasant emotions and never to unpleasant ones. From an emotional point of view own advantages feel good and the advantages of different individuals tend to feel bad. Thus it can't be expected from small children that they have an objective sense of justice. Those properties are also valid in the adult age what can be seen for example in excessive salaries of members of the board.

4.2.5 Preservation of the own physical integrity (health): DOWEL

Definition: *DOWEL* [du:wel] (abbreviation of “*I do feel well*”) denotes the GE which develops automatically from the perception of a preservation of the own physical integrity.

The most important asset of an individual is its own health (or its own physical integrity, respectively). If a stability or even an improvement of the own physical integrity is perceived then the DOWEL detector activates a signal in the form of the pleasant GE (DOWEL). The centre of this cognitive GE impulse is the own health, i.e. the own physical (including mental) integrity of the perceiving individual. DOWEL appears when a constant or an improving own health level is perceived compared to the last perceived own health level (the status quo ante). Thus the relative but not the absolute health level is crucial for the generation of DOWEL [Edwards, 1973; Diener, 1984; Watten, 1997; Hill, 2008].

The individual gains indications of a stability or improvement of the own health level by the self-observation of its body. Further indications are provided by feelings, for example by a declining pain. In addition, external hints can lead to such a perception such as regular laboratory results, good results of an examination, or plausible opinions of experts. An activation of DOWEL requires that the individual actually perceives the fact of a real or a probable stability or improvement of the own physical integrity. Without such a perception no DOWEL impulse is generated.

The DOWEL called GE is per se pleasant. This GE, which is activated by the perception of a preservation of the own physical integrity, usually occurs with a small to intermediate intensity. Typical expressions (or overall emotional manifestations) of DOWEL are joy, happiness, thankfulness, contentment, and confidence. However, if the individual felt a strong inner uneasiness (NOWEL) before the perception of a preservation of the own physical integrity then this perception can also merely lead to a relief (in the form of an instant reduction of the UE).

In a DOWEL situation (i.e. in a situation in which DOWEL prevails) often accompanying automatic thoughts appear. Such automatic thoughts focus on the cause of the GE generation, i.e. on the perceived preservation of the own physical integrity. Their contents are typically of descriptive nature (“I am better again now.”) or of commenting character (“That’s wonderful.”).

In and after a DOWEL situation individuals show different kinds of behaviour. The latter include to smile, to communicate with other individuals about the good or improving own state of health, to cease additional measures to preserve or improve the own state of health, or to omit any corresponding activities.

The function of the mechanism which generates DOWEL corresponds to a health detector. Its counterpart in the UE area which activates NOWEL works like an illness detector. Both mechanisms together activate the contrasting pair NOWEL–DOWEL and function like a detector for the own physical integrity which controls the physical integrity of the perceiving individual.

4.2.6 Favourable behaviour of a different power: UDIR

Definition: *UDIR* [ju:dir] (abbreviation of “*You did something right*”) denotes the GE which develops automatically from the perception of an appropriate behaviour of a different power.

The behaviour (or the properties) of other individuals or of inanimate objects can influence the perceiving individual or its goals in a positive way. If the UDIR detector detects a real or a probable appropriate behaviour of a different power then it activates a signal in the form of the pleasant GE (UDIR) in the perceiving individual.

The cognitive GE impulse UDIR refers to the behaviour (or the property) of a different power. This power has a material or an immaterial consistence and is part of the living world (of the same species or of a different species) or of the inanimate world. A power of the living world can be a single individual or a group of individuals (including an organization).

Examples for such a power include a helpful friend, a responsible politician, a well-behaved child, or a reliable technical device.

This power shows a behaviour, i.e. an action or an omission, which is classified as appropriate by the perceiving individual. An appropriate behaviour is an (intentional or unintentional) behaviour which evokes a wanted pleasant feeling in the perceiving individual or which corresponds to the opinions (or beliefs, respectively) of the perceiving individual. Examples for such an appropriate behaviour of a different power are a nice word of the partner, a praise, an important goal of a player of the favourite soccer club, the joyful greeting by the own dog, or a nice weather during holidays. Thus often a different cognitive GE impulse (for example ITWOUT, RESPECT, LIKIT) precedes the activation of UDIR. Nevertheless, UDIR can also appear independently, i.e. without a preceding positive feeling.

As described in its definition, an automatic generation of UDIR requires that the individual

actually perceives that a different power is responsible for an own positive feeling or for an own favourable situation. If this perception lacks then no UDIR impulse is generated. The UDIR called GE is per se pleasant. This GE, which is activated by an appropriate behaviour of a different power, typically appears with a small to intermediate intensity. Typical expressions (or overall emotional manifestations) of the GE are joy, enthusiasm, thankfulness, or pride.

Automatically upcoming thoughts in a UDIR situation (i.e. in a situation in which UDIR dominates) refer to the cause of the GE activation, i.e. to the perceived appropriate behaviour of a different power. Their contents are usually of descriptive nature (“He passed his exam.”) or of commenting nature (“Well done.”).

In and after a UDIR situation an individual can act in different ways. Those kinds of behaviour include to smile, to laugh, to approach the other power in a friendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically), to communicate with other individuals about the appropriate behaviour of the other power, or to omit any activities.

UDIR often leads to a friendly approach to the other power. Verbal forms of such a friendly approach include to agree with the other power, to praise it, to pay the other power compliments, to congratulate the other power, or to thank the other power. Non-verbal forms are to applaud, to cheer, or to reward the other power by giving a present (e.g. a professional promotion, a raise, a food, or another form of present). The physical forms of a friendly approach include to shake hands (as a sign of congratulation, of thank, or of admiration), to pat the other power on the back, or to embrace the other power.

An own behaviour which is fuelled by UDIR and which is showed to the other individual (for example in the form of a compliment or a thanks activates a pleasant RESPECT in the other individual and thus automatically a positive assessment of the originator of this pleasant emotion. Thus an individual which expresses a high regard to a different individual, is positively assessed automatically by this inter-individual UDIR→RESPECT cascade. This inter-individual cascade serves the building and rapport of social relationships (for example friendships). However, this is a mutual thing, i.e. both sides have to endeavour to activate pleasant emotions in the other individual. The inter-individual UDIR→RESPECT cascade is also of great importance in the bringing up of children (in order to motivate children to repeat a favourable behaviour).

This cascade effect also explains the *Stockholm syndrome*. In 1973 kidnappers took several bank employees hostage in Stockholm for several days. In this time the hostages paradoxically seemed to ally themselves with their torturers. They showed loyalty to the criminals and even supported them in their doing. At first glance this behaviour of the hostages seems to be unexplainable. However, the inter-individual cascade just described explains the course of events. Being in acute danger of his or her life it is not advisable to evoke negative feelings in the criminals. More likely it helps to evoke positive emotions which then react automatically upon the originator. By asking for the motifs of the criminals and by showing a honest understanding for them the hostages achieved precisely this effect and increased their chances of survival (because nobody kills his or her accomplice).

The cognitive GE impulse UDIR and the cognitive UE impulse UDINOR serve to regulate and optimize the relations of the perceiving individual to other individuals. That means that the behaviour of a different individual shall be influenced in such a way that the former leads to less unpleasant feelings, more pleasant emotions, or a greater correspondence with the own opinions.

The mechanism which generates UDIR in the perceiving individual corresponds to a detector

for an appropriate behaviour of a different power. Accordingly, its counterpart in the UE area which activates UDINOR works like a detector for an inappropriate behaviour of a different power. Together both detectors (which activate the contrasting pair UDINOR–UDIR) have the function of a detector for the behaviour of a different power of the living world or the inanimate world which continuously checks for correspondence with the needs of the perceiving individual.

4.2.7 Favourable own behaviour: IDIR

Definition: *IDIR* [aidır] (abbreviation of “I did something right”) denotes the GE which develops automatically from the perception of an own appropriate behaviour.

Of course also the own behaviour can have favourable effects on an individual or on his or her goals. The IDIR detector detects such an appropriate own behaviour. If such an appropriate own behaviour is discovered then the IDIR detector activates a signal in the form of the pleasant GE (IDIR).

The centre of the cognitive impulse IDIR is thus the own behaviour of the perceiving individual. The latter perceives an own behaviour, i.e. an action or an omission, which it classifies as appropriate. An appropriate behaviour is – like in a UDIR situation – an (intentional or unintentional) own behaviour which evokes a wanted pleasant feeling in the perceiving individual or which corresponds to the own opinions (or beliefs, respectively) [Hoppe, 1931] of the perceiving individual. Such an appropriate own behaviour is for example a social, a scholastic, or a professional success which has been achieved by the personal performance of perceiving individual. Often a different cognitive GE impulse (e.g. ITWOUT, NOTINA) precedes the activation of IDIR.

As described in the definition of IDIR the generation of IDIR requires that the individual perceives (or recognizes) an own appropriate behaviour (which lead to a favourable own situation). Only such a perception enables the generation of IDIR in the perceiving individual. If this perception lacks then a generation of IDIR is not possible.

The IDIR called GE is per se pleasant. This GE, which is generated by the perception of an own appropriate behaviour, typically appears with a small to intermediate intensity. Typical expressions (or overall emotional manifestations) of IDIR are joy, happiness, self-affirmation, elation, a feeling of triumph, or proud.

In an IDIR situation (i.e. in a situation in which IDIR dominates) often automatic thoughts (i.e. automatically generated thoughts) appear. Their contents focus on the perception of an own appropriate behaviour and are typically of descriptive nature (“My presentation was excellent.”) or of commenting character (“My preparation was worth the effort.”, “Well done!”).

In and after an IDIR situation an individual has different behavioural options. Those include to smile, to laugh, to cheer, to approach the own appropriate behaviour or the own person in a friendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically; e.g. blowing one’s own trumpet, gestures of triumph), to communicate with other individuals about the own appropriate behaviour (or the success, respectively), to celebrate, to reward oneself, or to omit any special activities. The individual can further strive to repeat its behaviour or a similar one in the future in order to experience the pleasant emotion IDIR again.

The non-verbal area offers various body language signals to humans in order to express an own success. Some of those gestures resemble the ones which appear in ITWOUT situations.

Widely spread gestures include to raise the arms, to raise the index finger, or to raise the fist. Western sportsmen sometimes beat with the fist in the air in case of an own success and extend this gesture often with a jump in the air. Jocular western gestures in the case of an own success are to pat oneself on the own shoulder or to breathe on the nails of the own hand in order to polish them on the own revers [Morris, 1994].

A typical consequence of IDIR is that humans tend to classify their own reasoning and their own behaviour as absolutely correct – even if this contradicts the reality or the rules of the logic. A reasoning consists of one or several assumptions (e.g. “The road is wet.”) and of an inference (e.g. “Therefore it must have rained.”). The reasoning is logically correct if the assumption (or the assumptions, respectively) as well as the inference are correct (in the former example the inference sounds plausible but it is wrong: the road can have become wet because of other reasons than rain). But the human reasoning and behaviour are regarded as error-prone and as often irrational. A study during the financial crises in 2008 regarding the behaviour of experienced professional stock-brokers revealed that they massively trusted their own beliefs even if the latter were based on logically invalid inferences. The stock-brokers showed severe problems to give up their existing beliefs [Knauff, 2010]. This phenomenon is not restricted to stock-brokers. Humans generally tend to show difficulties to disengage themselves from vastly anchored thinking.

A typical phenomenon which is based on IDIR consists of the *self-serving error*. The self-serving error designates the fact that humans like on the one hand to assign successes to themselves (i.e. to the own ability, to the own behaviour) and on the other hand to refuse the responsibility for failures and to assign the latter to external causes (e.g. to the behaviour of other individuals, to unfavourable circumstances, to an unfair treatment, to an impossibility of a better own behaviour) [Hoppe, 1931]. This behaviour is widely spread, is repeatedly confirmed in studies, and can already been observed in childhood. The explanation for the self-serving error bases on the pleasant character of IDIR: it just provides the individual a pleasant emotion to be responsible for a (even only accidentally developed) success. On the other hand individuals try to avoid unpleasant IDINOR situations by assigning bad own performances to external causes. This desire is so strong that subjects not even shy away from corresponding deceits [Hoppe, 1931]. Such a behaviour can be advantageous for an individual by preventing enduring diffuse IDINOR situations. However, in the medium-term this behaviour harms the perceiving individual when useful changes of the own behaviour and the learning from failures do not happen.

Also stereotypes are favoured by IDIR. To reaffirm one’s beliefs (or opinions) or to see them (seemingly) affirmed evokes a pleasant emotion (IDIR) in the perceiving individual: “I am right.”, “That’s like it is.”, “I always knew it.” This action is one reason why stereotypes are difficult to change² and why people in a positive mood are more inclined to stereotypes (the use of the stereotype fosters the preservation of the own good mood).

The mechanism which generates IDIR in the perceiving individual functions like a detector for an own appropriate behaviour. Analogously, its counterpart in the UE area which activates IDINOR works like a detector for an own inappropriate behaviour. Together both mechanisms (which activate the contrasting pair IDINOR–IDIR) work in the sense of a detector for the own behaviour which checks the own behaviour of an individual on consistency with the own needs and beliefs.

² Other reasons are that stereotypes can also activate the pleasant HAVAD (since the debasement of other individuals implies an own advantage) and RESPECT (in a group of like-minded people).

4.2.8 Perception of an attractive object: LIKIT

Definition: *LIKIT* [laikit] (*abbreviation of “I like it/this”*) denotes the GE which develops automatically from the perception of a strong similarity to a positively valued component of the individual value system.

The LIKIT detector identifies objects which the perceiving individual likes. If the detector recognizes such an object then it generates a signal in the form of the pleasant GE (LIKIT). In this way the LIKIT detector supports the individual in the quick assessment of the continuing stream of impressions to which it is exposed and in the differentiation of the wanted from the unwanted ones.

This cognitive GE impulse is based on the individual value system of the perceiving individual. The individual value system denotes the (virtual) totality of all current values and assessments of an individual of its world, plus the corresponding assessment mechanisms (for an extensive description see [Tscharmi, 2020]). Beside those mechanisms it includes many separate components to each of which a specific (often variable) value (or valence) is assigned [Stein, 1990]. Each (real or abstract) object that can be valued can form the basis of such a component. Such an object has a material or an immaterial consistence. It is part of the inanimate world or of the living world (of the same species or of a different species).

Examples for such an object are a food, a sound, a piece of music, a colour, a smell, a different individual, a species, a certain place, an event, a specific fashion accessory, a literary work, a newspaper, an activity, a kind of sport, a school subject, an opinion, or an abstract concept. Comparable to the position of a slide control, a positive or a negative value (valence) is then assigned to each of those components. A positive value means that the individual likes this component (or the underlying object, respectively). A negative value on the other hand means, that the individual refuses this component (or the underlying object, respectively). Most values of the individual value system change with time. The assignment of a value to a component is carried out by one or several automatically working mechanisms. Some values depend on the age of the individual, they are subject to mechanisms of the *age-related assessment*. Other values are affected by the *body state-related assessment*. Again other values are innate and regulated by *on innate values-related assessment* mechanisms.

Of great importance is the automatic *feeling-related assessment* mechanism. If a pleasant feeling, for example a cognitive GE impulse, is generated in an individual then an object of relation (e.g. the originator of this pleasant feeling) to this pleasant feeling, i.e. an object which the perceiving individual can relate to the generation of this feeling (e.g. causal, temporal), is positively assessed automatically. For example if the perceiving individual experiences a respect for the own personality and the activation of the pleasant RESPECT, then the originator of this respect (typically a different individual) is assigned automatically a positive (precisely: a more positive) value in the individual value system of the perceiving individual (so to speak the slide control is adjusted towards a more positive value). For example the philosopher Johann Gottlieb Fichte had good-natured father who loved his son sincerely. Fichte replied this love and admired him. In the year 1791 he noted: “The good, warm-hearted, upright father! How well does always his sight, his tone, and his reasoning to me!” [Kühn, 2012]

On the other hand, if an unpleasant feeling, for example a pain or a UE impulse, is generated in an individual then an object of relation (e.g. the originator of this unpleasant feeling) to this unpleasant feeling, i.e. an object which the perceiving individual can relate to the generation of this feeling (e.g. causal, temporal), is negatively assessed automatically (so to speak the

slide control is adjusted towards a more negative value).

If the individual perceives later an object which strongly resembles to or equals a positively valued component of its individual value system then the cognitive GE impulse LIKIT is generated automatically. On the other hand, if the individual perceives an object which strongly resembles to or equals a negatively valued component of its individual value system then DISLIKIT is activated automatically. Typical examples for positively valued objects which activate LIKIT include a nice picture, a sunrise, a friend, a beloved person or pet, the favourite food if hungry, the favourite activity, the favourite school subject, the favourite colour, the ode to the joy from Ludwig van Beethoven, the sunshine, or a rise in salary or in pocket-money. After this manner, the individual value system enables a rapid emotional assessment of new situations by an automatic emotional learning.

The LIKIT called GE is per se pleasant. This GE which is activated by an own preference can appear with a small to a very high intensity. The various expressions (or overall emotional manifestations) of LIKIT reach from joy, pleasure, appetite, liking, preference, lust, gloating, happiness, elation, elevation, and enthusiasm to love and euphoria. Love occurs worldwide [Aron, 2005].

It is typical for LIKIT that this cognitive GE impulse comes along with a tendency to approach the perceived object [Cabanac, 1979] (e.g. in the form of interest, of attention, of turning to the object, of taking possession). Lewin designated this tendency to approach an object with a positive valence as a driving force [Lewin, 1951]. The tendency to approach a positively valued object can even be seen in the involuntary movement of the human pupil: if a person looks at an object that he or she likes then the pupil involuntarily dilates (as if the eye would like to let through as many optical information as possible from the pleasant object). This reflex can't be controlled voluntarily. Oriental jade dealers thus often wear dark glasses in order to prevent their eyes from betraying themselves. And also professional poker players shield their eyes in order to hide the reactions of their pupils on a good set of playing cards [Morris, 1994].

In a LIKIT situation (i.e. a situation in which LIKIT prevails) automatic thoughts can appear in addition to the emotion (i.e. LIKIT) and to the automatically arising behavioural reaction (i.e. the tendency to approach the perceived object). Those automatic thoughts refer to the cause of the GE generation, i.e. to the positively valued object that has been perceived. They are typically of descriptive nature (“Food is ready.”) or of commenting nature (“Delicious!”). Typical kinds of behaviour of an individual in and after a LIKIT situation are to smile, to approach the object in a friendly (verbally, non-verbally, physically; e.g. in order to take possession of the object) or an unfriendly way (verbally, non-verbally, physically; e. g. in order to take possession of the object, stalking), to approach the object again in the future, to communicate with other individuals about the object or the own preference, to seek help (e.g. in order to take possession of the object), or to omit any special activities.

There are various human gestures in order to signal his or her own preferences. Some of those gestures are dependent on culture, others are widely or worldwide spread. One of those gestures in Central Europe is to kiss the own hand-ring in order to express that something is delicious. Thumb and index finger form a vertical ring, before the tips of thumb and index finger smoothly touch the lips and the hand shoots forward. In South America symbolizes a palm pointing to the ground of a forearm which is hold parallel to the ground that something is delicious: “Es muy delicado.” Different gestures express that a man likes a woman. In Europe and North America one of them is to symbolically outline the female upper part of the body with both hands. Both hands describe a curvaceous silhouette of a female body. In

Brazil the gesture “eye with a “telescope”” is very popular. Both hands form a pipe in front of an eye in order to give the impression that the gesticulating person looks through a telescope to a beautiful woman who is present. Women indicate to their interlocutor that they find him handsome by running their fingers through their hair. Other gestures serve to indicate that a person loves a different person. Those include to touch the own heart or to kiss the own finger tips and to blow then the kiss across to the beloved person [Morris, 1994]. Further non-verbal forms of respect are to embrace a different individual, to (unconsciously) mirror his or her behaviour, to cast a longer glance at the other person, or to give a present to the other individual.

A frequent consequence of a LIKIT with a stronger intensity is the desire to *take possession* of the perceived object. The reason for this desire to take possession of the object is that objects which activate positive feelings are considered as and work like resources. A resource of an individual includes anything what is able to generate a positive (i.e. pleasant) feeling in the perceiving individual. After objects have been taken into possession they have to be marked as the own possession (e.g. by an entry in the land register, by a wedding ring) or they have to be protected against a taking away (e.g. by fences, by locks, by social rules (for example in the form of laws)). To take an object into possession often leads in the individual to a pride of possession, i.e. to a joy at the acquired object.

In their leisure time people often do things which appear to be nonsensical, unnecessary, or even dangerous from the perspective of the survival of the own genes. Such *leisure activities* include parachuting, bungee jumping, climbing, riding a motorbike, skiing, and the collecting of stamps. Why do people engage in such seemingly useless activities? The answer is obvious: because people enjoy doing those activities. The latter evoked a pleasant GE in the individual in the past (often in the form of ITWOUT) what automatically lead to a positive assessment of those activities. This positively valued component of the own individual value system then automatically activates LIKIT if the underlying object is perceived again by the individual. To do the leisure activity again promises to activate further pleasant GE – even if this is coupled to dangers to life and limb.

Most values in the human individual value system are of individual nature and form during life by the feeling-related assessment mechanism. However, there are also innate human preferences. The latter include the strict preference for sweet food of new-born babies, the desire for children of women, and the unquestioning love of most mothers for their offspring. A further, influential, innate preference which occurs in humans and in many higher species consists in the *baby schema*. The baby schema designates the childlike proportions of body and face. Remarkably few marks characterize this baby schema. Among them are big eyes, chubby cheeks, and a relatively large head with a high forehead [Lorenz, 1943]. Also young ducks, young European hares, or young lions have those qualities. Already 12-18 months old infants react to those characteristics without any previous corresponding experience. The baby schema leads to an emotional approach which fosters a protection, a care, and a long lasting raising of the parents. The enormous power of the baby schema is extensively used in the doll and in the comics industry.

There are various other *key stimuli* in the animal kingdom beside the baby schema. Key stimuli are stimuli which lead to a specific, often innate behaviour. Such stimuli are available for almost all sensory areas. For example, an egg has to be spotted in order to be incubated by the herring gull. The smell of blood triggers the search for prey of sharks. The red male belly is a signal for approach for female sticklebacks. The redder the belly the more attractive is the fish for the female [Eibl-Eibesfeldt, 1967]. Such key stimuli in the animal kingdom should not

be underrated since similar stimuli are at work at humans too. For example, merely the sight of pornographic material often leads to masturbation at men – although no woman who wants to copulate is nearby. Also advertising uses plenty of (often female) sexual signals in order to attract attention [Eibl-Eibesfeldt, 1967].

The object of an own positive assessment can also consist in the perceiving individual itself. A stronger own positive valuation is called self-love. It is characterized by pleasant emotions (LIKIT). An excessive self-love is called *narcissism*.

Different individuals have different individual value systems. That means that different individuals like different things. The resulting variety often appears interesting and inspiring. But one has to be firmly warned that there are persons who get pleasure from torturing other people [Ekman, 2003]. They disavow their victims (often in a subtle way), disparage them in order to socially isolate them, and torture them emotionally and physically with the goal to destroy them. At the same time they silently enjoy to voyeuristically watch the harm that they caused. The French victimologist Marie-France Hirigoyen brilliantly described with blunt openness this type of culprit whom she called narcissistic perverse [Hirigoyen, 1998]. Those individuals have a highly narcissistic disposition, enhance their own ego by the systematic and often subtle destruction of other individuals, act coldly and pitilessly, disregard all moral values, and experience a boundless inner pleasure and no scruple at all in their destructive doing.

The described mechanism which activates LIKIT in the individual functions like a preference detector. Analogously, the mechanism which generates DISLIKIT in the UE area works like a dislike detector. Both mechanisms combined activate the contrasting pair DISLIKIT–LIKIT and function like a valence detector which quickly classifies perceived objects according to their valence for the perceiving individual.

5. Evolutionary aspects of the cognitive GE impulses

Such as negative emotions, positive emotions developed during evolution by (natural) selection [Darwin, 1872]. Panksepp showed that the underlying neuronal systems of emotions and animals (of kin species) strongly resemble one another [Panksepp, 1998]. If the cognitive GE impulses (such as ITWOUT, NOTINA, RESPECT) developed as basic building blocks of positive emotions in nature over hundreds of millions of years then, inevitably, they have to be explainable by evolutionary aspects [Grinde, 2002]. Is this the case?

The generation of pleasant emotions in the form of the GE is intended to reward the perceiving individual for an in principle desirable development (e.g. for a goal attainment). On the other hand the generated pleasant emotions (GE) are a “promise for the future”: they motivate the perceiving individual to repeat such a desirable behaviour in the future in order to experience the pleasant GE again.

From an evolutionary perspective cognitive GE impulses must have provided advantages on average to the individuals in the past to pass on their genes compared to those individuals that did not possess those cognitive GE impulses. In this case, they could succeed in the course of long time periods within a species until finally every individual of the species possessed those characteristics (or those cognitive GE impulses, respectively) [Nesse, 2004].

NOTINA: An individual shelter- or comfort-seeking behaviour can be observed from the

vertebrates to the protozoa [Scott, 1969]. An individual with a detector with NOTINA generation is rewarded with a pleasant emotion (GE) by this detector if the individual finds or creates a safe place (e.g. a safe place for the night). The perception of this pleasant emotion (NOTINA) tends to motivate the individual to seek again such a safe place in the future. Its motivation to do so is therefore higher compared to individuals that do not have this characteristic, i.e. compared to individuals without detectors with NOTINA generation (which do not experience such a rewarding, pleasant emotion despite being at a safe place). Thus individuals with detectors with NOTINA generation make greater efforts on average to seek a safe place compared to individuals without detectors with NOTINA generation. However, the stay at a safe place increases the chance of survival of the individual and its offspring because of the reduced vigilance during sleeping. In addition, safe places for the night often serve to raise offspring and thus have a second function [Kappeler, 2006]. Individuals with detectors with NOTINA generation therefore have a longer lifetime compared to individuals without detectors with NOTINA generation. A longer lifetime increases the opportunities for reproduction [Kappeler, 2006]. More opportunities for reproduction lead to more descendants on average. Thus individuals with detectors with NOTINA generation have a higher fitness compared to individuals without detectors with NOTINA generation. After this manner, the characteristic “detector with NOTINA generation” could spread more and more among the individuals of the species until finally all individuals of the species had it at their disposal.

ITWOUT: In the nature, the goal attainment is of fundamental importance since the goals of adult animals primarily serve the fulfilment of basic needs (such as the search for food, the defence against enemies, the reproduction). The ITWOUT detector rewards the individual for a progress towards the goal attainment with a pleasant emotion (ITWOUT). This reward increases the motivation of an individual with detector with ITWOUT generation to reach its goals. Such an individual thus makes greater efforts on average to reach its goals compared to an individual without detector with ITWOUT generation (which is not rewarded by a pleasant emotion when reaching its goals). Since a higher goal attainment in nature often serves the own survival or that one of the own genes and therefore leads to a longer lifetime and more opportunities for reproduction, individuals with detectors with ITWOUT generation have a higher fitness compared to individuals without detectors with ITWOUT generation.

Therefore, the characteristic “detector with ITWOUT generation” could spread more and more in the course of time until all individuals of the species had this characteristic finally.

RESPECT: In case of the perception of a respect for the own personality (by a different individual) the RESPECT detector activates a pleasant emotion (RESPECT). Therefore individuals prefer those other individuals which are well-disposed towards them and their goals. This in turn enhances their chances to achieve their own goals and reduces the risk of being hurt by aggressive conspecifics compared to individuals without detectors with RESPECT generation. This increases the lifespan, the opportunities for reproduction, and the fitness of individuals with detectors with RESPECT generation compared to individuals without detectors with RESPECT generation. Therefore the characteristic “detector with RESPECT generation” spread more and more within the individuals of the species in the course of time until all individuals of the species had this characteristic finally.

HAVAD: The HAVAD detector rewards the individual with a pleasant emotion (HAVAD) in case of the perception of an own advantage in areas, which are important to the individual. This motivates individuals with detectors with HAVAD generation more to carry through own advantages, to increase them, or to put them on show compared to individuals without detectors with HAVAD generation. This increases on average the resources and the

advantages of individuals with detectors with HAVAD generation. The achievement of a high rank in the group hierarchy provides the individual also special advantages, for example the priority at the feeding place, at the sleeping place, or in the reproduction [Eibl-Eibesfeldt, 1967]. This increases the opportunities for reproduction on average (also as a consequence of a higher attractiveness because of more resources and more power [Pérusse, 1994]), increases the number of the descendants and thus the fitness compared to individuals without detectors with HAVAD generation. Therefore, the characteristic “detector with HAVAD generation” spread more and more over a long period of time until finally all individuals of the species had it at their disposal.

DOWEL: The DOWEL detector rewards the individual for a stable or an improving own physical integrity with a pleasant emotion (DOWEL). This tends to motivate the individual to take appropriate measures to preserve or improve the own physical integrity. This incentive is missing for individuals without detectors with DOWEL generation. Individuals with detectors with DOWEL generation therefore have a longer lifespan on average, what increases their opportunities for reproduction and their fitness compared to individuals without detectors with DOWEL generation. Over a long period of time the characteristic “detector with DOWEL generation” therefore spread more and more among the individuals of the species until all individuals of the species had the characteristic finally.

UDIR: Individuals with detectors with UDIR generation tend more than individuals without detectors with UDIR generation to reward other individuals for an appropriate behaviour after experiencing the pleasant UDIR impulse. However, a positive feedback (for example in the form of a present) evokes a positive emotion (RESPECT) in the other individual and therefore increases the motivation to get further pleasant feedbacks in the future. This animates the other individual to repeat its obviously good behaviour. But such a repetition directly serves the goals of the perceiving individual. Individuals without detectors with UDIR generation achieve such a development less often since they are not motivated by a pleasant cognitive GE impulse to give a positive feedback. Thus individuals with detectors with UDIR generation have a longer lifespan on average, more opportunities for reproduction, and a higher fitness compared to individuals without detectors with UDIR generation. The characteristic “detector with UDIR generation” thus won through finally in the individuals of the species.

IDIR: The IDIR detector activates a pleasant emotion (IDIR) in the individual if it perceives an own appropriate behaviour. This emotional incentive tends to motivate the perceiving individual more to repeat the appropriate own behaviour than this is the case for an individual without detector with IDIR generation. However, an appropriate own behaviour serves in nature often the own survival or that one of the own genes (e.g. the search for food, the defence against threats, the reproduction). Therefore individuals with detectors with IDIR generation reach a longer lifespan on average, more opportunities for reproduction, and a higher fitness compared to individuals without detectors with IDIR generation. In this way the characteristic “detector with IDIR generation” could spread more and more in the course of time until all individuals of the species had this characteristic finally.

LIKIT: Quick and correct assessments which products of nature (such as fruits, plants, or animals) are eatable or which places provide safety and protection are of critical importance for the survival of the individual and its genes. Therefore the existence of an individual value system (which comprises the preferences of the individual) is of crucial importance [Stein, 1990]. A detector with LIKIT generation thus provides individuals a clear advantage of survival compared to individuals without detectors with LIKIT generation. This leads to a

longer lifespan for individuals with detectors with LIKIT generation on average, what increases their opportunities for reproduction and their fitness. Therefore the characteristic “detector with LIKIT generation” spread more and more among the individuals of the species in the course of time until all individuals of the species finally had this characteristic. In summary, it can be stated that the cognitive GE impulses can be explained conclusively from an evolutionary point of view. Cognitive GE impulses provide higher chances of survival to their owners on average. Emotions are based on neuronal systems which shall secure the survival of individuals and their genes [Lang, 2010]. Aspects like goal attainment (ITWOUT), individual safety (NOTINA), intimacy in individual relationships (RESPECT), higher physical attractiveness or higher power (HAVAD), health (DOWEL), and high-quality food (LIKIT) have been important for individuals during the whole evolution [Hill, 2008].

6. Discussion of the cognitive GE impulses

Beside the indicative and to the present related form (e.g. for ITWOUT: “It does work out (like I want it to)”) all cognitive GE impulses have also automatically appearing subjunctive forms (e.g. subjunctive, to the present related ITWOUT: “It could work out (like I want it to)”). The activation of subjunctive cognitive impulses works in the same manner as the one of the corresponding indicative forms. However, for subjunctive cognitive GE impulses there has to be a high probability that the corresponding event will in fact occur. Furthermore, many cognitive GE impulses have also to the past related forms (e.g. indicative, to the past related ITWOUT: “It did work out (like I want it to)”) or to the future related forms (e.g. indicative, to the future related ITWOUT: “It will work out (like I want it to)”). Also for the forms which are related to the past or to the future, the assessment always takes place in the present (“...(like I want it to”). The automatic assessment about the past or the future always takes place at the current moment (for example that a furtherance of an own important striving in fact has taken place or that it will take place).

Which factors lead to positive emotions in other cultures? Lu looked into the generation of positive emotions in Chinese societies. Chinese people experience positive emotions when they perceive the gratification of personal desires (ITWOUT); when they perceive peace, a peaceful life (NOTINA); when they perceive being loved, being respected, harmonious interpersonal relationships (RESPECT); when they perceive material abundance, downward social comparisons (HAVAD); when they perceive own physical health (DOWEL); when they give warmth to other people (UDIR); when they perceive a sense of own achievements and worth, self-control (IDIR); and when they perceive family or societal values (LIKIT) [Lu, 2001]. Different cognitive GE impulses can appear shortly after each other in different combinations. All positive emotions (such as thankfulness, confidence, pride) consist of one or several of those basic elements.

An amazing property of cognitive GE impulses is that they can be generated also voluntary (this is contrary to the cognitive UE impulses with the exception of DISLIKIT). For example an enthusiastic voluntary thinking about an own success can evoke ITWOUT or IDIR in the perceiving individual. A further example for the voluntary activation of cognitive GE impulses can be seen in ecstasy states.

The accompanying expressions (or overall emotional manifestations) of the cognitive GE

impulses (like joy, happiness, gratefulness) are widely unspecific concerning their underlying occurrences. That means that a certain expression does not always base on one and the same cognitive GE impulse but can be activated by different cognitive GE impulses. Exceptions are the feeling of superiority, the preference, or the love which are based on one and the same cognitive GE impulse (on HAVAD and on LIKIT, respectively).

Automatic thoughts appear relatively sparse with cognitive GE impulses. Particularly there are usually no automatic mental mechanisms such as circle of thought or scene building of thought which keep an activated elementary emotion alive (as this is the case for cognitive UE impulses). This is not amazing since cognitive GE impulses signal favourable developments to the perceiving individual which do not need any current changes. The lack of extensive automatic thoughts is advantageous for the perceiving individual. The sparsely appearing automatic thoughts bring a pleasant emotion (GE) and positive contents. Because of their rareness they hardly distract the individual from its current activities. The mind, the attention, and the striving of the individual remain undisturbed and are even inspired since the automatic thoughts, the cognitions, and the emotions point to favourable circumstances [Nesse, 2004] or confirm the individual in its personality or its behaviour. From this perspective the positive emotions based on cognitive GE impulses enhance the possibilities of an individual [Fredrickson, 2008].

The generation of cognitive GE impulses sometimes influences the behaviour of the perceiving individual. However, most general behavioural options are available for all GE impulses. Thus from a certain behaviour it can often not be inferred to the underlying cognitive GE impulse. A certain behaviour of the individual because of the activation of a cognitive GE impulse can directly follow the latter or appear with a temporal delay. Often the individual continues its striving, intensifies, interrupts, or stops it. Frequently the individual shows a behaviour which aims to repeat the activation of the generated GE impulse.

Like for cognitive UE impulses the human emotional activities of positive emotions consist typically of three phases. The centre of the first phase is the detection of a favourable occurrence. If this perception succeeds then one of the eight logical cognitive GE detectors activates the pleasant GE. In the second phase (sparse) automatic thoughts appear and convey positive contents. The third phase is characterized by the behaviour of the individual which is induced by the cognitive GE impulse. Note that phase two and phase three do not necessarily have to appear.

There are dispositional differences in the generation of cognitive GE impulses. Those differences appear for example due to the different individual value systems of different individuals.

Positive emotions foster the exploration behaviour (i.e. the discovery of something new), the long-lasting occupation with a certain topic (e.g. the raising of children), the learning, and the creativity. They serve the well-being of the individual and strengthen its health [Bucher, 2018].

Thus positive emotions have many positive effects on an individual. But positive emotions have not merely positive consequences [Nesse, 2004] – the negative consequences of positive emotions should not be underestimated. People eat too fat and too sweet because of the resulting pleasant (positive) emotions. For the same reason they engage in dangerous leisure time activities, take drugs, drink too much alcohol, smoke cigarettes, or waste their money in the game of chance. Those kinds of behaviour show that the archaic, emotion-driven drives do not always fit well to the modern times. Positive emotions enhance the thoughtlessness and blindness to dangers [Nesse, 2004]. An indication of this fact can be seen in the extreme

experience of positive emotions during a mania, the counterpart of a depression. Manic people are characterized among other things by an unusual positive mood, an ecstatic unwavering optimism, an over-estimation of one's abilities, a superficial thinking, a reduced need for sleep, a preparedness to take disproportionately high risks, and excessive kinds of behaviour (e.g. an excessive buying behaviour, an excessive drug abuse, an excessive sexuality, an excessive aggressiveness, a pronounced urge to talk). Manic people tend to risk all their resources (money, health, relationships). Also a fresh love which can generate very high positive emotions is characterized among other things by an exaggerated optimism, the transfiguration of the loved object and the emotional dependence on the loved object, a reduced need for sleep, and the ignoring of dangers [Aron, 2005]. Frequently those effects tempt the individual in love to careless and unfavourable behaviours (e.g. to take increased risks, to attach to an unsuitable partner, to be susceptible for deceit). Love reduces the control and the cognitive abilities [van Steenberg, 2014]. Other studies show that people in a positive mood recognize less liars and defrauders [Forgas, 2008]. Moreover, people in a positive mood can be easier impressed by weak arguments [Bless, 1990]. Positive emotions tempt individuals to take higher risks (for example concerning their health) [Grant, 2011]. Thus the own positive emotions can lead to massive unfavourable consequences for the perceiving individual. In addition, positive emotions which other people experience can have an adverse effect on the perceiving individual. Positive emotions motivate other individuals to mobbing, to bossing, and to the abuse of power. Positive emotions fuel people with an inhuman cast of mind. Positive emotions motivate defrauders and criminals to their voluntary planning and undertaking of unethical and inhuman crimes with the only goal to damage other people in order to gain own advantages. Similarly, positive emotions drive narcissistic individuals to wage war in small matters as well as in big. Thus, positive emotions do not have exclusively positive consequences on humans. Whereas negative emotions primarily affect the perceiving individual itself, positive emotions can enormously harm other individuals if their realization takes place at the expense of other individuals. Formulated from the view of the perceiving individual: the positive emotions of other people can massively harm the perceiving individual and lead to strong negative emotions or worse if ruthless other people realize their positive emotions voluntarily or thoughtlessly at the expense of other people.

Positive emotions do not always show the perceiving individual what is good for him or her. They merely reward the individual for higher, general aspects (e.g. a goal attainment) which were helpful on average for past generations to pass on their genes. For example, the GE which are activated during eating primarily reward for the eating itself and not for the quality of the ingested food. ITWOUT rewards by pleasant emotions merely the higher aspect of goal attainment – and not if the activity itself makes sense for the individual or whether it is desirable. ITWOUT appears also at activities like the game of chance or at the planning and commitment of crimes. Analogously, purposeful manipulations of swindlers activate RESPECT in the perceiving individual – but to the detriment of the latter. Vicious individuals exploit the generation of RESPECT to instigate other individuals to commit crimes. HAVAD motivates the individual to time-consuming activities such as the collection of beer mats or the collection of wealth at the expense of other individuals. UDIR and IDIR appear also after having committed terrible crimes in the corresponding individuals. And IDIR fosters generally the impression that the own behaviour is okay. At long last, an individual is always responsible by itself how intensively he or she lets himself or herself seduce by own positive emotions and in what way he or she shapes the own individual value system. However, it is

becoming problematic if individuals start to enrich themselves at the expense of other individuals or even begin to kill other people. An appropriate reply to such reckless kinds of behaviour can only be given by the corresponding societies – or by the evolution at last.

In the human brain the amygdala is of importance in the case of rewards [LeDoux, 2008]. It projects (especially from the basal and the accessory basal nucleus) to the nucleus accumbens, the cerebral reward centre. Also the ventral tegmental area (VTA) projects to the nucleus accumbens (directly and indirectly via the amygdala and the BNST, respectively). The VTA is activated by eating chocolate when hungry, by monetary gains, by love, by learning, by sex, and by cocaine [Aron, 2005]. Neurons from the VTA release dopamine in the nucleus accumbens. Neurons of the nucleus accumbens on the other hand release endogenous opioids in large areas of the frontal brain [Spitzer, 2002]. Furthermore, positive emotions activate the insula [Craig, 2008] and the cingulate cortex. That humans experience pleasant emotions peripheral below the brain skull could be due to projections of the dopaminergic modulation system into that area. Also the serotonergic modulation system projects into that area. Serotonin is synthesized from tryptophan which humans ingest from food like meat or noodles. The serotonergic projection may explain the “noodle-high”, a distinct elation that a hungry person experiences if he or she eats a plate of noodles.

7. General remarks to the cognitive impulses

With good reasons it has been repeatedly emphasized that an activation of a cognitive impulse can only take place if the individual perceives the underlying occurrence. The ability of humans to simultaneously and consciously perceive several events at the same time are limited. Many experiments show this difficulty. In one of those experiments subjects watched a video in which three persons with white T-shirts played basketball against three persons with black T-shirts. The task for the subjects was to count the number of the passings of the team with the white T-shirts. Afterwards, the subjects were asked for the number of passings and whether they noticed something special in the video. It turned out that two thirds of the subjects did not notice that a gorilla has walked through the scenery [Simons, 1999]. The counting of the passings deflected the attention from the rest of the events. Other investigations as well as individual experience show that people have severe difficulties with multitasking. Already the ringing of the own mobile phone (without answering it) distracts a driver and increases the accident risk [Holland, 2013]. Since with the consciously guided own attention virtually only one thing at one moment can be processed and since this limited capacity is a bottleneck given the multitude of simultaneously occurring stimuli, an automatic cutting out of currently seemingly unimportant stimuli takes place. This effect causes among other things that changes of the UE during the simultaneous activity of automatic thoughts (which demand the attention) are badly noticed and remembered. Also, if the individual is distracted by external factors then occurrences which normally activate emotions (like a goal attainment, a theft attempt) are not (or too late) noticed. And in case of two simultaneously occurring feelings the stronger one usually drowns the other [Darwin, 1872]. The last-named peculiarity of the (human) emotion system makes sense: if several feelings appear at the same time then the individual should take care first about the strongest one (which is usually also

the most important one). If a UE and a GE appear simultaneously then the UE has usually the higher intensity and the GE is not experienced primarily. The automatic focus on the stronger feeling possibly explains why the intensity of unpleasant emotions typically exceeds the one of pleasant emotions: the perceiving individual shall first take care about the cause of the unpleasant emotion – which is potentially dangerous for the individual – and not about the cause of the pleasant emotion.

The limited abilities to consciously perceive several events at the same time inevitably lead to the fact that the course of emotions is badly remembered. Even the place on the body where the elementary emotions are experienced is badly remembered. Similarly, the detailed content of the various automatic thoughts in a UE situation is badly remembered too. Better remembered is the general fact that one had a bad time.

The cognitive GE impulses and the cognitive UE impulses are reciprocal to each other, i.e. each cognitive GE impulse has a counterpart in the UE area and vice versa (e.g. ITWOUT–ITNOUT). Also several simple impulses show this reciprocity (e.g. hunger–ingestion of food, urgent need to empty the bowels–bowel movement, sexual drive–orgasm) and some feelings of the FSW class (e.g. feeling of cold–feeling of warmth) [Cabanac, 1979]. Interestingly, some simple impulses do not have such a counterpart. For example, the quenching of thirst (which activates a GE) lacks such a counterpart in the UE area. Why thirst (beside its sensory impressions like a dryness of the mouth) does not activate a UE remains unclear. Perhaps the archaic feelings thirst and hunger should remain clearly bodily distinguishable from each other during their evolutionary development.

The eight reciprocal pairs of cognitive impulses consisting of one cognitive UE impulse and one cognitive GE impulse (i.e. ITNOUT–ITWOUT, SOTINA–NOTINA, NESPECT–RESPECT, HASAD–HAVAD, NOWEL–DOWEL, UDINOR–UDIR, IDINOR–IDIR, DISLIKIT–LIKIT) refer to fundamental aspects of the survival of an individual and its genes: the goal attainment, the safety of own resources, the friendliness of other individuals, the advantages concerning resources, the own health, the behaviour of other individuals and objects, the own behaviour, and the quick assessment of the valence of objects. Those reciprocal pairs developed during evolution to provide the perceiving individual the possibility to deal with specific situations [Nesse, 2004]. Those eight survival aspects lead to the activation of emotions in the individual.

The eight cognitive UE impulses and the eight cognitive GE impulses are the basic elements which form all emotions (such as jealousy, nostalgia, envy, elation). For example, in case of jealousy typically (and dependent on the situation) SOTINA, HASAD, NESPECT, or UDINOR appear. Thus emotions base on an automatic unconscious cognitive processing of information which stem on the one hand from actual sensory impressions and on the other hand from the memory of the individual. The result of this specific information processing (for example via pattern recognition) reaches in case of conspicuousness in the form of emotions or automatic thoughts the consciousness of the individual. Those information shall there be processed on a conscious level and, if necessary, lead to an appropriate behaviour. Emotions and automatic thoughts work like the mouthpiece of the unconsciousness. Emotions are a reaction to external and internal events which are of importance for the perceiving individual.

The cognitive (GE and UE) impulses base on logical detectors. Like nature developed first specific sensory cells in order to detect a certain fact (e.g. light, an injury) and then combined several cells to a sense organ in order to enhance the quality of detection (e.g. to the sense organ eye), in the same manner many neurons work together in a logical sense in order to

generate cognitive GE and UE impulses from already otherwise existing information (e.g. from visual, acoustic, or stored information). Combined those neurons function like logical detectors, logical sensors, or logical sense organs and serve the detection of a certain occurrence. No cognitive impulse of the human emotion system bases directly and merely on an appropriate physical detector.

Interestingly the functional requirements of a cognitive detector are not very strong. In essence a cognitive detector consists of two basic functional units: the detection unit and a memory which is assigned to the detection unit (and which for example stores the appropriate patterns which shall be detected). The real work is done by the detection unit. The composition of the detection unit is such that it can recognize certain characteristics of the object or the event which shall be detected. Those characteristics exist in an appropriate stored form. The detection unit then scans the stream of the current perceptions of the individual as well as stored information in order to detect correspondences with those characteristics. Thus the cognitive detectors have the following profiles:

– *ITNOU*: detection unit for the recognition of a real or possible hindrance and for the comparison with the current goals of the individual + assigned memory with the current goals of the individual + memory with the next steps towards those goals

– *ITWOUT*: detection unit for the recognition of a real or probable furtherance and for the comparison with the current goals of the individual + assigned memory with the current goals of the individual + memory with the next steps towards those goals

– *SOTINA/NOTINA*: detection unit for the pattern recognition of real or possible dangers which threaten the own resources + assigned memory with the specific dangers for the individual

– *NESPECT*: detection unit for the pattern recognition of real or possible signs of disrespect for the own personality + assigned memory with the specific signs of disrespect

– *RESPECT*: detection unit for the pattern recognition of real or probable signs of respect for the own personality + assigned memory with the specific signs of respect

– *HASAD/HAVAD*: detection unit for the comparison of real or possible resources (which are also claimed by the perceiving individual) of other individuals with the own resources + assigned memory with the resources which are claimed by the perceiving individual

– *NOWEL/DOWEL*: detection unit for the comparison of the own current real or possible physical integrity with the last perceived own physical integrity level (the status quo ante) + assigned memory with the last perceived own physical integrity level

– *UDINOR/UDIR*: detection unit for the recognition of an unfavourable development and for the comparison with a real or possible past behaviour of a different individual + assigned memory with the past behaviour of different individuals

– *IDINOR/IDIR*: detection unit for the recognition of an unfavourable development and for the comparison with an own real or possible past behaviour + assigned memory with the own past behaviour

– *DISLIKIT*: detection unit for the pattern recognition of individual disliked objects + assigned memory with the individual disliked objects (of the individual value system)

– *LIKIT*: detection unit for the pattern recognition of individual liked objects + assigned memory with the individual liked objects (of the individual value system).

A memory which is assigned to the detection unit has to save at least one element in order to enable the cognitive detector to function. However, in humans (and many other species) the number of stored elements exceeds this minimum by far. The stored elements are either available in a fixed and invariable (i.e. in an innate) form or in a variable (i.e. in a learned)

form. In case of UDINOR and UDIR and IDINOR and IDIR there is the possibility of either a short-term or a long-term storage of the corresponding information. The storage duration for ITNOUT and ITWOUT has to match at least the actuality of the individual goals. The functional construction of the cognitive detectors described above explains also why small children are not yet able to recognize dangers: their memories which are assigned to the cognitive UE detectors simply still lack the information, or elements (i.e. the specific dangers), which are required for the recognition of and defence against dangers.

Since all cognitive UE impulses base on one and the same emotion – the elementary emotion UE – and all cognitive GE impulses base on another emotion – the elementary emotion GE – there is an inherent ambiguity concerning the interpretation of the cause for an activated elementary emotion. In nature this potential ambiguity is irrelevant for the survival of the individual since the UE signals danger (which leads to a quick flight or to an aggressive reaction). The answer to the question which detector activated a current UE gives either the external event which occurred at that time (e.g. the perception of an insult) or the thought which was in the consciousness of the individual at that time (e.g. “Did I safely lock the front door?”). In order to interpret the own emotions correctly it is thus crucial to pay attention to the current situations and to the automatic thoughts. Only in that case the perceiving individual is able to classify upcoming emotions correctly and to react appropriately. A big advantage provides the knowledge about the function of the cognitive impulses since it provides the individual a simple classification scheme. Also the exclusion principle helps to determine the currently active cognitive UE detector.

The perhaps biggest danger for a society with equal rights starts out from the contrasting pair HASAD–HAVAD. In the UE area as well as in the GE area cognitive impulses foster the extension of own advantages at the expense of other individuals. They reinforce a one-sided sense of justice in the perceiving individual since the advantages of others are experienced unpleasantly and own advantages are experienced pleasantly. This perspective favours discrimination, inconsiderateness, exploitation, abuse of power, and crimes against humanity in the name of the own group affiliation. Both cognitive impulses stir up morally reprehensible expressions of the UE and the GE towards other individuals like hatred in the case of HASAD and arrogance and ecstasy of power in the case of HAVAD.

Finally, the activation of emotions if the perceiving individual is not primarily involved itself but merely observes the situation of a different individual from outside (i.e. the vicarious emotions) is interesting (e.g. if the perceiving individual observes the ITNOUT situation of a different individual). Such an observation does not also activate a UE in the perceiving individual but a GE (for example in the form of an amusement) – provided that the other individual does not come to any harm (if the latter is the case then often DISLIKIT appears). Analogously the observation of cognitive GE impulses of a different individual does often not also activate a GE in the perceiving individual but a UE (in the form of DISLIKIT).

8. Conclusions

This paper describes a novel emotion model. It relies on the fact that all positive emotions (such as joy, pride, thankfulness) base on the same emotion: a pleasant feeling, the GE, which can be felt in the head. Similarly, all negative emotions (such as fear, envy, impatience) base

on the same emotion: an unpleasant feeling, the UE, which can be felt in the gut. Those elementary emotions are automatically activated in the individual by physical detectors (or receptors, respectively) and especially by eight logical detectors. The latter control higher survival aspects of the individual like the own goal attainment, the safety of the own resources, the friendliness of different individuals, the advantages of own resources or the ones of other individuals, the own health, the behaviour of other individuals, the own behaviour, and the recognition of the valence of objects. By the generation of cognitive impulses those detectors alarm the individual if dangers are discovered or reward the individual if favourable occurrences are detected. Those cognitive impulses shape the negative and positive emotions.

The knowledge of the function of cognitive impulses (or of the underlying logical detectors) enables the individual to analyse appearing emotions more precisely and to react more competent in critical situations. With the aid of the model presented here, emotions can be named more clearly and understood better. The human activation of emotions follows remarkably simple and clear rules. Although being simple, the activation rules can lead to complex appearing behaviour.

Also from an evolutionary point of view cognitive impulses can be explained consistently. They are independent of the composition of the available senses (or receptors) of an individual. Nature has hold the structure of the cognitive impulses (as described in their definitions) flexible what makes them universally effective, independently of the concrete composition of the environment or of the individual. There are indications that cognitive impulses could (in a functional respect, not in the form of emotions like in humans) already exist in biological cells in the cascades of molecular signals. The UE would then be represented by one or several leading signals. In that respect, cognitive impulses possibly form a fundamental basic structure for self-organized systems of all kind.

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